

RESEARCH ON INTER-ORGANIZATIONAL RELATIONS: A BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY

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SUMMARY

The growing chaos in the literature on inter-organizational relations makes it a fertile field for quantitative studies that clarify the conceptual map and complement existing qualitative studies. These only reflect the point of view of a few expert researchers and therefore a skewed view of the state of the art. In this context, a quantitative bibliometric study serves to shape the state of the art. In this work, a bibliometric study highlights the existing theoretical fragmentation in the literature on inter-organizational relations and cartography of the most relevant works and theoretical approaches, as well as highlights the most discussed topics in the field.

KEY WORDS: Inter-organizational relationships, Cooperation, Alliances, Bibliometrics, Citation analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Research into inter-organizational relationships is becoming increasingly popular as a mechanism to resolve the paradox of competitive agility (Osborn, 1998), whereby organizations need to be flexible in order to cope with a hyper-competitive environment (D'Aveni, 1994), while at the same time being stable in order to learn and grow thanks to the development of their strengths.

Broadly speaking, inter-organizational relationships involve a voluntary agreement between two or more companies that means ongoing exchanges, sharing capital, technology, or other specific assets, or jointly developing new products and technologies (Ireland, Hitt, Camp y Sexton, 2001).

Due to its topicality, there are few studies that resolve the real state of the art in research on inter-organizational relations (see Grandori and Soda, 1995; Osborn and Hawthorn, 1997; Oliver and Ebers, 1998; García and Medina, 1998; Gulati, Nohria and Zaheer, 2000). In addition, these works are qualitative in nature and reflect the point of view and experience of only a few expert researchers and, therefore, a biased view of the field, although no less valuable for that.

In this context, a bibliometric study can serve, despite its limitations, to shape the state of the art. This paper analyzes the most representative quotes collected in a collection of research on relationships interorganizativas as well as the frequency with which they are cited together, as an indicator of proximity between them, which could make it possible to delimit schools of thought. The validity of this technique for exploring the intellectual structure of a scientific discipline has been demonstrated by numerous studies (Small, 1973, White and Griffith, 1981; McCain, 1986; Culnan, O'Reilly and Chatman, 1990; White y McCain, 1998; Ying, Gobinda and Schubert, 1999).

The graphical representation based on the joint citation of the most influential works in the discipline replaces the criterion of a small group of experts, as happens in qualitative reviews of the literature, with that of as many experts as there are works analyzed. However, it is not intended to replace qualitative analyses of the state of the art, but rather to complement them with a more objective technique, necessary for unconsolidated fields of research that, like this one, suffer from a high degree of fragmentation (García and Medina, 1998).

Documents with high frequencies of co-citation tend to be grouped together when mapped, so the maps obtained reflect the joint decisions of a large number of authors rather than the judgment of a small group of experts, as in comprehensive literature reviews with qualitative approaches.

These graphs could be considered as the image of the field shaped by the work of its protagonists, they can collect the evolution of researchers, show relationships between fields and establish how closely some disciplines are related to others. Maps serve to reveal which scientific topics have been most actively researched and which individuals, publications, and institutions are currently preeminent in an area of research (Garfield, 1986).

There are two contributions made by this work. The first is aimed at demonstrating how bibliometric analysis can contribute to clarifying the state of the art in a discipline that is little explored or in formation. The second contribution is to shed some light on the state of the art of research on inter-organisational relations.

2. METHODOLOGY

Traditionally, bibliometric analyses have been classified into two categories, depending on whether they lead to activity indicators or relationship indicators. The former provide data on the impact or influence of research activities, while the latter track the links and interactions between researchers and fields, so that the contents of the activities and their evolution are described (Callon, Courtial and Penan, 1993). At the same time, this work has been carried out in two distinct stages. In the first, a citation analysis is carried out, consisting of the counts of the citation frequencies of the bibliographic references used by a sample of representative articles of research on interorganizational relations, which, from now on, we will call a sample citante. In the second stage, the technique of joint citation analysis was applied to trace the relationships between the most influential works and identify schools of thought and research topics current during the period analyzed.

Research articles on inter-organizational relations, published in a set of journals selected by a panel of experts from among the most influential research journals in the area of business management, were used as a sample (Tahai and Meyer, 1999).

The choice of the article over other sources of documentation such as books, doctoral theses or conference proceedings is based on its consideration of certified knowledge, understood as knowledge that has been subjected to the criticism of colleagues and that has passed the test of their objections (Callon *et al.*, 1993).

Given the citation analysis nature of this work, the primary source of information was the *Social Science Citation Index* (SSCI). It is a citation index managed by the *Institute for Scientific Information* (ISI) in the United States that has collected the content of approximately 4,100 journals worldwide since 1972. Despite the time span covered by the database, the period studied was from 1992 to February 2001 due to the availability of access through the Scientific Information Center of Andalusia (CICA). However, the novelty of the topic and the size of the sample make the selected period considered representative of the current state of the art.

Once all the articles published during the analysis period were retrieved, after a filter of key terms related to the discipline, they were manually reviewed to reject those that were not related to the field of study. Thus, for example, the use of the term "networks" as a keyword for the search yielded both articles dealing with the subject of strategic networks of companies and works on computer networks, which had to be excluded. Thus, the cited sample was reduced to 319 articles directly related to the field analyzed.

After this, a database was built with all the bibliographic references used by the authors of the cited sample. To ensure the reliability of subsequent citation counts, this database had to be painstakingly cleaned by hand, to avoid spelling and coding errors of the citations and to take into account only the first editions of the books. Although in its origins the analysis of joint citations was carried out using the cited work as the unit of analysis, the difficulty of its treatment has meant that the methodology has been developed on the analysis of citations of any work by a given author, that is, on his complete work. However, although similar in their approaches, the second approach suffers from important limitations and leads to results that are difficult to interpret, especially in disciplines as multidisciplinary as Business Administration, which encourages an author to make relevant contributions to the discipline from different approaches. For this reason, in this work, the cited work or document has been used as the unit of analysis.

Based on the stages at which an analysis of joint citations of authors is normally performed, the steps used in the analysis of joint citations of documents are described in more detail below. This technique is based on counting the frequency of a set of representative articles of research in a given scientific discipline, with which a pair of documents is cited simultaneously. White and Griffith (1981), McCain (1990), and White and McCain (1998) describe this procedure in detail for application to the analysis of co-citations of authors. Its validity in exploring the intellectual structure of a scientific discipline has been demonstrated by numerous works (see Small, 1973, White and Griffith, 1981; McCain, 1986; Culnan *et al.*, 1990; White and McCain, 1998; Ying *et al.*, 1999).

In order to map the intellectual base of research on inter-organizational relations, the 26 most influential works identified in the previous citation frequency count were selected, responding to a citation threshold of at least 10% of the works in the citing sample. Although the first 85 most cited papers were previously considered (for at least 5% of the articles observed), the graphical representation of them was not very clarifying and

fragmented, as predicted by other more qualitative studies on the discipline (see García and Medina, 1998), and the goodness-of-fit indicators did not ensure the reliability of the results obtained.

The elaboration of the maps is carried out by obtaining Pearson's correlation coefficient between the joint citation profiles of each pair established among the 26 most cited works. For the construction of this measure, the distribution of frequencies with which all the works that are part of the bibliographic references made by the citing sample are cited is obtained. From it, all possible pairs are formed among the 26 most cited documents and how many articles cite each established pair are counted.

The counts obtained are arranged in a square and symmetrical matrix, whose main diagonal is left undefined. Subsequently, this raw citation matrix is converted to a matrix whose coefficients reflect the desired proximity measure.

To this end, almost all studies that carry out analyses of joint citations of authors use Pearson's correlation coefficient as a measure of proximity (McCain, 1990; White and Griffith, 1981; White and McCain, 1998). Although this study performs an analysis of joint citations of papers, this treatment has also been chosen for at least two advantages. First, for a given pair of papers, Pearson's correlation coefficient functions as a measure, not of the frequency with which that pair of papers were cited (the raw frequency count), but of how similar their co-citation profiles are to the rest of the papers considered: two papers that are always cited together with a third paper, but rarely with others, they will have a high and positive correlation and can be said to be perceived as related or similar in some sense by the citing sample. Second, the correlation coefficient also avoids differences in scale between works that are highly cited and those that have similar citation profiles but are less so (Kerlinger, 1973; White and McCain, 1998).

For the treatment of the main diagonal in the calculation of correlation coefficients there are two possibilities. The first (White & Griffith, 1981) considers the diagonal value resulting from dividing the sum of the three highest values by two, which could indicate in a general way the relative importance of a particular work within the field; the other way (McCain, 1990), simply considers these data not available to calculate the correlation coefficients and applies the criterion of eliminating these two cases to obtain the correlation coefficient (*pairwise delete*).

In the present study, the second treatment was adopted because after performing both analyses, no significant differences were observed in the configurations obtained. For this reason, and for simplicity's sake, we chose

not to consider the values of the main diagonal in the calculation of the correlation coefficients between pairs of documents.

The next step of the research was aimed at obtaining the coordinates of the units analysed in a small space for their subsequent graphic representation and interpretation. The statistical technique selected was that of multidimensional scales, hereinafter MDS (*MultiDimensional Scaling*). MDS analysis requires an object proximity matrix as inputs. This procedure allows maps to be obtained from the proximity matrix between the elements analyzed, so that the underlying structure of the set can be studied. In the analysis of co-citations, the main use of the MDS procedure is twofold: on the one hand, it provides information about co-citation relationships and, on the other hand, it helps to identify the underlying relationships observed in their sites (McCain, 1990).

Documents with similar joint citation profiles tend to appear grouped in the new configuration. Thus, those jobs that are closely related to others tend to be in a central position in the "intellectual space," while those with weak relationships tend to be located on the periphery. In this way, central or peripheral specialties, schools of thought or other intellectual groups should be easily identified.

The output of MDS is a table with the coordinates of each document in a two-dimensional space. Its main purpose is to capture as much information as possible from the original data in only two or three dimensions, i.e., to reduce the dimension of space. This simplification necessarily distorts the original distances and cannot explain all the variance collected in the proximity matrix.

The statistical package used summarizes the distortion with a goodness-of-fit statistic called "*stress*" which, broadly speaking, captures the difference between the distances between points in the initial configuration and those obtained in the final configuration. The assessment of the fit obtained can be complemented with a graphical representation that confronts the original distances in abscissas and the distances between points obtained in the new configuration in ordinates, so that, with the appropriate scale, a point cloud configured on the diagonal can be indicative of the goodness of the fit (*Sheppard graph*). On the other hand, the goodness of fit depends directly on the number of units analyzed, so that the greater the number of units to be mapped, the worse the values of the goodness-of-fit statistic. Therefore, this was an additional reason that led to mapping only the first 26 most cited works, thus obtaining an adequate *stress*.

With the coordinates calculated for each document, the new configurations obtained were represented on a plan. In summary, the distances observed on the maps give an idea of the similarity between two papers, as measured by Pearson's correlation coefficient between the co-citation profiles with the remaining twenty-four papers.

3. RESULTS OF THE BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY

3.1. The Joint Citation Map

Figure 1 shows the map of jobs represented according to the technique described in the previous sections. In this map, the numbers are equivalent to the order of citation, with the number one being, for example, the most cited work by all the articles analyzed in the cited sample studied. The representation of the works in this two-dimensional map would be located in the position where the number in question has been represented (and not where the label with the name of the first author and the year has been placed). Next to each issue, the author of the issue and the year of the work are mentioned. In the case of more than one author, only the first of these is mentioned².

Figure 1. Intellectual basis of research on inter-organizational relationships.

Source: Authors' own creation

As already mentioned, in a consolidated field of study it is to be expected that the presentation on the map of groups of works characteristic of the different schools or disciplines that deal with the subject in question or, also, of the most important topics in the subject. However, and coinciding with the arguments defended by García and Medina (1998), inter-organizational relations are dealt with by a fertile but fragmented literature. In this sense, groups become difficult to form, and instead of schools there is a mixture of theoretical approaches with topics of the field of study.

Next, the descriptive treatment of the information represented on the map is carried out. In this way, the groups of jobs that are detected are analysed, the location of distance or proximity of these groups to each other, and the existence of borderline or distant jobs that, regardless of the group in which they are located, are very close or very far from other specific jobs.

3.2. Working groups

A first approximation allows us to see within the announced fragmentation two large groups, divided in Figure 1 by a dashed line. In general terms, the upper group is made up of works related to theoretical developments, while the lower group is dominated by the treatment of topics in the field of inter-organizational relations.

More specifically, the top group encompasses those works that constitute the conceptual frameworks used in the treatment of inter-organizational relationships. The distances between the different works represented within this group allow us to deduce that, although there is a broad multidisciplinary (García and Medina, 1998), the necessary eclectic approach has not been commonly adopted (Tsang, 2000).

In this first group, three subgroups are distinguished, both by the content of the works and by the distances represented on the map, leaving the rest of the works without viable grouping. The first subgroup, consisting of Burt (1992) and Granovetter (1973), discusses the nature of the links between organizations. The importance of relationships and the social dimension allows Larson (1992) and Granovetter (1985) to be grouped into a second subgroup.

The third subgroup represents the approach to the topic of inter-organizational relationships by transaction cost economics (TCE), supported almost exclusively by the work of Williamson (1975, 1985, 1991). The rest of the authors, despite the fact that they have been cited with a high frequency, do not have high similarities in joint citation, so they do not consolidate conceptual schools within the field analyzed. The work of Porter (1980), with his contribution of the structure-behavior-results paradigm to industrial organization, has been widely cited; the work of Powell (1990), who defends inter-organizational relations as an organizational form distinct from those of the market and hierarchy; the institutional approach to the work of DiMaggio and Powell (1983); the resource dependency theory of Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) that has served to analyze the struggle for power within inter-organizational relations; and the work of Thompson (1967), with his pioneering study of cooperative strategies and coalition formation.

Among the related works, it should be noted that Porter's work is not directly related to the work on inter-organizational relations. Its high frequency of citation in the analyzed sample is related to the number of times it is cited when all the works are analyzed, for example, in the *Strategic Management Journal* (see Ramos and

Ruiz, 2001). This effect could be called "inertial citation", and is due to the tendency to inexcusably cite certain works of great impact and recognized prestige in the area of knowledge, regardless of their direct relationship with the subject matter of each work.

The second group, under the dashed straight line in Figure 1, represents an amalgam of works that could be labeled, depending on the case, as topic-oriented or more empirical. The first thing that can be observed at first glance is a smaller distance between the different jobs, in relation to that which existed in the first group. This closeness demonstrates a higher rate of joint citation, except in two cases: the work of Nelson and Winter (1982) on evolutionary theory³, and that of Contractor and Lorange (1988) on cooperative strategies in international business.

As in the previous case, different subgroups can also be formed. A first subgroup would contain those works that have provided important bases for the discipline in two of the most cited forms of inter-organizational relations: *joint ventures* and alliances. In this way, other forms of relationships such as franchising, licensing or subcontracting agreements, among others, receive less attention within the jobs with the greatest impact in the field.

In terms of contributions on joint ventures, this subgroup includes the work of Kogut (1988), which deals with the capacity of *joint ventures* to learn and increase market power; Hennart (1988), on an application of transaction cost theory to equity, and for whom joint ventures can be explained as a means of avoiding inefficient markets for intermediate inputs; and Harrigan (1985), who discusses when cooperation through *joint ventures* will be preferred rather than through other forms of cooperation.

With regard to alliances, Hamel's (1991) work on the determinants and asymmetries of learning among the members of an alliance is located in this subgroup, arguing that the value of an alliance can come from the benefit derived from the successful execution of joint tasks, or from internalizing the skills of allies; Hamel, Doz and Prahalad (1989) analyse factors on which the success of an alliance depends, such as convergence of strategic objectives, divergence of competitive objectives, size, market power or inter-organisational learning; Parkhe (1993), who studies the structure of alliances and their connection to performance, based on game and transaction cost theories; Ring and Van de Ven (1992) study four forms of governance of alliances based on risk and the need for trust: discrete, recurrent, relational contracting and hierarchical managerial transactions;

and, finally, Hagedoorn (1993), which attempts to clarify the motives that guide the company to cooperate in its efforts to innovate.

A second subgroup would include those works dedicated to one of the topics most discussed in this literature: learning. Some of the studies overlap with the previous subgroup, such as those of Hamel (1991), Kogut (1988) and Hamel *et al.* (1989). In addition to these, the work of Cohen and Levinthal (1990) is located within this group, in which they deal with the concept of absorptive capacity, understood as the ability of the firm to recognize the value of external information, assimilate it and apply it for commercial purposes; and the work of Doz (1996), which analyzes learning in strategic alliances along dimensions such as the environment, the task, processes, skills and objectives, forecasting how different learning processes can determine the success or failure of the partnership.

A final subgroup can be identified, consisting of only two papers. This subgroup analyzes the evolutionary process of the alliance and frames the work of Ring and Van de Ven (1994), which presents a processual framework that explains how and why interorganizational relationships emerge, evolve and dissolve; and that of Gulati (1995), which seeks to overcome the approach to transaction costs which, according to Gulati, wrongly treats each transaction as independent and ignores the role of trust that emerges from repeated alliances between the same firms. It is worth noting the high impact of this last work, given that despite being one of the most recent, 1995, it ranks sixth in terms of the frequency with which it is cited.

3.3. Location of groups

As discussed above, two large areas can be distinguished in Figure 1 by a horizontal dashed line. The works in the upper area represent some of the conceptual frameworks that have been most used, from sometimes diametrically different perspectives such as the social one (Granovetter, 1973 and 1985; Larson 1992), the mechanisms of governance employed (Williamson, 1975, 1985, 1991), industrial organization (Porter, 1980), institutional theory (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983), resource dependency theory (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978), or, from a strategic management approach, Thompson's (1967) pioneering notions of cooperative strategies. The works of the lower area, as also mentioned, are oriented to the study of specific topics related to learning and knowledge management, the formation and evolution of alliances and *joint ventures*, etc.

The previous theoretical frameworks and topics discussed have led to the formation of different working groups. However, it is also interesting to analyse the position of some groups in relation to others. Just as the closeness between two works indicated a similar citation profile and, therefore, the possible formation of schools, the closeness between groups would indicate the intimate relationship of the topics treated or theoretical approaches used.

In this sense, the theoretical works of the upper area show, due to their distances, that they are usually cited in a combined way on few occasions, except in the case of social networks (Granovetter, 1985; Larson, 1992) and transaction cost theory (Williamson, 1975, 1985, 1991). The reasons for this joint high citation are twofold. The first is based on the importance of some social topics such as, for example, the trust or reputation of people (which can be extended to organizations), in the decision of the most appropriate forms of governance and in the development, or not, of opportunistic behaviors among the members of a relationship. The second reason, rather than complementarity, shows the antagonism of the works that rely on the concept of social networks and that cite the works of the economics of transaction costs with critical intentions, since they consider transactions between companies to be discretionary, instead of continuous and based on long-term relationships and based on trust between people.

With regard to these two groups, transaction costs and social networks, it is important to highlight their centrality, a clear sign of their important role as the intellectual basis of the entire discipline. These two groups serve as a hinge for dealing with very different topics in the field of inter-organizational relations, and for making comparisons with other alternative theoretical approaches, which is very often the case due to the discipline's need for an eclectic approach (Tsang, 2000).

Within the first area, the group dedicated to ties in inter-organizational relations (Burt, 1992; Granovetter, 1973), is located in a peripheral position diametrically opposed to the contributions on the economics of transaction costs and, moreover, far from all the work in the second area. This contrasts with its high frequency of citation, which could be due to the fact that it is a group without a fixed citation pattern and that it is cited indistinctly with other works with which it does not reach the school form.

With regard to the second area, dedicated to more specific topics in the field of inter-organizational relations, it can be observed that the works that deal with the topic of *joint ventures* (Kogut, 1988; Hennart, 1988; Harrigan, 1985) and alliances (Hamel, 1991; Hamel *et al.*, 1989; Parkhe, 1993; Ring and Van de Ven, 1992; Hagedoorn,

1993) have been merged into a single subgroup, when they could have been represented separately. However, the close relationship between these works has led to considering them together.

This group, on the other hand, is frequently cited in works that rely on the topic of learning and knowledge management (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Doz, 1996; Hamel, 1991; Kogut, 1988; Hamel *et al.*,1989). This is evidenced both by the closeness between these groups and by their overlap in three of the studies (Hamel, 1991; Kogut, 1988; Hamel *et al.*,1989).

The relationship management group (Ring & Van de Ven, 1994; Gulati, 1995), in turn, also shows, due to its proximity, a direct relationship with the two previous groups. In this case, it is again evident that they are part of the same intellectual base, generating a similar literature in terms of the citations it uses.

3.4. Correlation matrix

The analysis of the correlation matrix of the joint citation of the cited works allows us to see which are those works that are cited together more and less often. It is especially interesting to highlight the borderline studies (*borderline* in the terminology of White and McCain (1998), which are those that, despite their high correlation, are part of different groups due to the difference of the topics treated. These borderline works are true bridges between the different topics addressed by the discipline.

Coinciding with the conclusions of previous sections, selecting those pairs of works with a correlation greater than 0.90 can be observed the high interrelation of the work groups related to *joint ventures and alliances*, evolution of the inter-organizational relationship, and learning. In order of correlation, the most correlated studies are: Kogut (1988) and Hamel *et al.* (1989), Hamel (1991) and Hamel *et al.* (1989), Hennart (1988) and Hagedoorn (1993), Ring and Van de Ven (1992) and Ring and Van de Ven (1994), Kogut (1988) and Hennart (1988) and Gulati (1995) and Doz (1996). The work of Kogut (1988) and Hamel *et al.* (1989), and de Hamel (1991) and Hamel *et al.* (1989), represent the intersection between the group dedicated to learning issues in cooperatives and that of *joint ventures* and alliances. Kogut (1988) and Hennart (1988) also have a high correlation, although perhaps their works cannot be considered borderline because Kogut's is part of both groups. The work of Ring and Van de Ven (1992) and Ring and Van de Ven (1994) bridges the gap between the group dedicated to evolution and that of *joint ventures*

and alliances, as is the work of Gulati (1995) and Doz (1996), which connect the work of learning with the work of the evolution of inter-organisational relations.

In short, despite the fact that some of the previous studies have been concentrated in different groups, the existence of high correlations reveals the artificiality of these separations, and that these studies could well belong to a single and large group called "characteristics, evolution and learning in inter-organizational relations". Again, it is difficult to detect the schools that other bibliometric studies have detected more easily in more consolidated and defined disciplines of study (see, for example, White and McCain, 1998, on information science).

Regarding the least correlated studies, the following stand out, in this order: Hamel (1991) and DiMaggio and Powell (1983), Hamel *et al.* (1989) and DiMaggio and Powell (1983), Hamel (1991) and Granovetter (1973), Kogut (1988) and DiMaggio and Powell (1983), and Hagedoorn (1993) and Granovetter (1973).

Although the extreme and peripheral location of the works of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) and Granovetter (1973) within the map already suggested that, despite the importance of the frequency with which they are cited, there would not be a clear pattern of citation with most of the works in the study, the analysis of the correlation matrix highlights this fact especially with two groups of works. On the one hand, work on learning in *joint ventures* or alliances (Hamel, 1991; Hamel *et al.*, 1989; Kogut, 1988) seem to have little to do with a possible institutional explanation of the phenomenon (which is the framework established by DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). On the other hand, the strength of the weak bond as an important element in the structuring of social networks (Granovetter, 1973), does not seem to have much to do, at least in the opinion of the aforementioned sample, with the learning processes that take place in alliances (Hamel, 1991), nor with the motives that guide companies to cooperate in their efforts to innovate (Hagedoorn, 1991). 1993).

4. LIMITATIONS

Carrying out a bibliometric study to know the state of the art of a certain subject and, in addition, of the literature on inter-organizational relations, has its limitations. In the first place, the documents analysed as the source of the bibliometric study are only a small part of the research activity on inter-organisational relations, so the

conclusions provided are limited in scope. However, due to the scientific journals studied, the selected sample is sufficiently representative of the literature in the area of knowledge of business organization. Therefore, the limitations of this sampling are similar to those of any statistical sampling.

Second, it is impossible to distinguish whether the citations were made to criticize the work or to rely on it; although, as López (1996) points out, when an author's work does not have quality, it is simply not cited.

In any case, the possible applications of the tool presented here have great potential for research in Business Administration. Its analysis can be applied to a wide variety of topics, especially those whose development is more recent, such as inter-organizational relations, for which there are still no extensive literature reviews. In this way, this type of study can be useful to identify the state of the art and detect the most influential authors, journals and works.

Finally, this type of study is useful for analysing the state of the art in an objective way, complementing and never replacing traditional qualitative methods of literature review. They can serve as a tool to identify the authors, papers, and journals most consumed by researchers in the discipline, as well as their relationships. Therefore, they can be useful to the researcher as a guide to identify the relevant literature of the subject to be studied, building the intellectual map of it and thus allowing an objective view of the field based on the behavior of its own protagonists.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this paper is to shed light on the state of the art in the literature on inter-organisational relations. This discipline suffers from great fragmentation (García and Medina, 1998) and has few studies of the state of the art (see Grandori and Soda, 1995; Osborn and Hawthorn, 1997; Oliver and Ebers, 1998; García and Medina, 1998; Gulati *et al.*, 2000) that turn out to be disjointed in part of their content and offer a biased and partial view, influenced by the profile of the authors who carry it out.

In this sense, bibliometrics offers an objective analysis of the opinion of a large number of authors with different tendencies and interested in different topics on the subject, whose validity for exploring the intellectual structure of a scientific discipline has been demonstrated by numerous works (Small, 1973, White & Griffith, 1981; McCain, 1986; Culnan *et al.*, 1990; White y McCain, 1998; Ying *et al.*, 1999).

The graphical representation of the joint citation profiles of the different works allows us to observe the lack of schools in the field of inter-organizational relations, as well as their fragmentation. This contradicts the assertions of some states of the art elaborated by authors that are based on a qualitative perception of the discipline.

Among the schools that can be detected are those based on the economics of transaction costs (Williamson, 1975, 1985 and 1991), and social networks (Larson, 1992; Granovetter, 1985) and the one dedicated to analysing the nature of the ties that relate both social and business networks (Burt, 1992; Granovetter, 1973). Also noteworthy are other works related to theoretical frameworks that do not consolidate schools in the discipline, but that are cited and used in a multitude of works, namely: the work of Porter (1980), with his contribution to the paradigm of structure-behavior-results, and which is subjected to a great shared inertial citation in the area of knowledge of business organization; the work of Powell (1990), which defines inter-organizational relations as an organizational form distinct from those of the market and hierarchy; DiMaggio and Powell's (1983) institutional approach to work; Pfeffer and Salancik's (1978) resource dependency theory; and Thompson's (1967) pioneering work on cooperative strategies and coalition building.

With regard to the working groups aimed at the specific treatment of topics related to the discipline, the formation of three groups of works that are closely related and even overlapping stands out. This overlap highlights the absence of polarization in the intellectual base that supports the treatment of key topics in the discipline. Thus, a large part of the articles analysed in the cited sample arise from a common strain of works that deal with the topic of learning and knowledge management in inter-organisational relations (Hamel, 1991; Kogut, 1988; Hamel *et al.*, 1989; Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Doz, 1996), their evolution (Ring and Van de Ven, 1994; Gulati, 1995), and the nature and characteristics of *joint ventures* and alliances (Kogut, 1988; Hennart, 1988; Harrigan, 1985; Hamel, 1991; Hamel *et al.*, 1989; Parkhe, 1993; Ring and Van de Ven, 1992; Hagedoorn, 1993).

Although the citing sample can be considered sufficiently representative, in order to further deepen the structure of the discipline, the citation threshold could be lowered to expand the number of cited works subject to analysis. In this sense, preliminary tests were carried out with the 85 most cited authors. The representation of these showed the growing importance of new schools, such as the resource-based vision of the company.

However, in view of this extended map, the high heterogeneity of the papers, the multiplicity of the topics analysed and, therefore, the difficulty of grouping papers, on the one hand, as well as the lesser goodness of the fit, on the other, gives rise to great uncertainty as to whether it would be appropriate to extend the present analysis from 26 to 85 papers.

In this sense, a future line of research that could be viable is to make representations of the main authors, as discussed in the methodology, rather than specific works. This could more clearly represent the formation of schools, but it suffers from the limitation that these authors could have a multidisciplinary production that would throw some distortion into the study.

Finally, it should be clarified that it is not intended to establish a quantitative methodology that replaces the realization of qualitative states of the question, but rather, to complement them in circumstances of little definition of a discipline yet to be delimited.

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NOTES

¹ Academy of Management Journal, Academy of Management Review, Administrative Science Quarterly, California Management Review, Harvard Business Review, Journal of Management, Journal of Management Studies, Management Science, Organization Science, Organization Studies, Sloan Management Review y Strategic Management Journal.

² The fact that only the first of the authors is mentioned is a limitation derived from the use of the database *Social Science Quotation Index*. However, the references at the end of this work contain the names of all the authors of each work.

³ Although the work of Nelson and Winter is isolated in this map, in a similar map, but representative of the 85 most cited works (on which no work has been done due to the high dispersion and fragmentation of the works represented, as well as their worse fit, measured by the *stress*) is neatly grouped with the works of Barney (1991), Wernerfelt (1984), Dierickx and Cool (1989), Penrose (1959) and Eisenhardt (1996). In this way, the resource-based vision of the firm in the treatment of inter-organizational relationships would be consolidated. A trend that has been consolidated much later than the rest of the theoretical works cited, so that it has not yet had the possibility of a greater impact on the current map, and to which Nelson and Winter contribute, among other things, with their concept of organizational routine.